

Justifying Consequentialist Justification

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Abstract

Moral theorists agree that moral domains require rational agents and that greater rational justification makes actions morally better. Like other people, they continue to disagree about the nature of justifying reasons. I begin with the common sense view that various directly experienced *pursue* and *avoid* states, such as pleasure, pain, vitality and fatigue, are intrinsic reasons to pursue or avoid those states. We call these kinds of states *good* and *bad*, the greater overall magnitude of which is greater rational reason to act and therefore more justified morally. Nonconsequentialists argue that overall better is not always morally better, but justifications of less good actions must in some way 1) matter but have no value and 2) not disrespect the losers in the suboptimal trade-off, which no theory adequately explains or provides. Most plausibly, consequentialist comparative value is the sole valid criterion of rational justification.

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Note to Readers

This paper is the product of a long-pursued goal, to describe the foundations of consequentialism and defend the greater good criterion in a journal-length article. Given the mass of literature, it is unsurprising that busy, anonymous referees have said the scope is unrealistic, but they have referred disappointingly little to the arguments. The fundamentals are not complex, and although the arguments are wide-ranging, they are assembled in a compact, coherent and I believe best explanation of moral justification. I invite readers to consider the arguments carefully and critically on their individual and collective merits. Comments and sharing are welcome.

Introduction

There are few circumstances more...unlike what might have been expected...than the little progress which has been made...respecting the criterion of right and wrong. From the dawn

of philosophy, the question concerning the ‘summum bonum’, or, what is the same thing, concerning the foundation of morality, has been accounted the main problem in speculative thought...And after more than two thousand years the same discussions continue (Mill 1985, 205).

John Stuart Mill hoped to close the discussion by showing that the summum bonum, or highest intrinsic good, is happiness, by which he meant pleasure and the absence of pain, to which all other goods are means. Accordingly, “Actions are right in proportion as they tend to promote happiness, wrong as they tend to produce the reverse of happiness” (1985, 210). Mill’s hedonic value theory remains controversial, however, as does the underlying claim that value – the “summum bonum,” hedonic or otherwise – is the same thing as the foundation of morality and sole criterion of right and wrong. The discussions continue.

§1 and §2 defend Mill’s propositions, essential to all versions of consequentialism, that intrinsic value, whatever its content, is foundational raw material of ethics and that comparative value, the greater good, is a criterion – the **GGC** – by which to prioritize, categorize and justify actions morally. Because the GGC is agnostic regarding the nature and content of value, and to facilitate discussion, §3 sketches a theory of value, inherent worth and respect. §4 through §7 argue that the GGC is *exclusively* justifying: It converges with Kant’s categorical imperatives as modified (§4); underlies and criterially supersedes social constructs (§5), intuitions and virtues (§6); and withstands other objections (§7). I formalize a version of the GGC (§8) and summarize (§9).

1. Analytic Basics

Words name concepts, which are the pragmatic categories human beings devise by which to model, reason and communicate about the world. Some words imply others, either as synonyms, like bachelor and unmarried man, or as essential correlates, like effect and cause or property and owner. Analytic implications follow from meanings as understood in context by competent language users.

The concept of a moral domain analytically requires, first, agents who can consider and justify choices and actions in ways others can recognize as being rational in kind, even if they disagree about the facts. Beings lacking this cognitive capacity are not moral agents, even if they are empathetic, cooperative or otherwise good. Second, greater rational justification analytically makes an action morally better than less justified actions.

2. The Greater Good is Rationally Justifying

“Good” is the first thing that falls under the apprehension of the practical reason, which is directed to action: since every agent acts for an end under the aspect of good... Hence this is the first precept of law, that “good is to be done and pursued, and evil is to be avoided”... so that whatever the practical reason naturally apprehends as man’s good (or evil) belongs to the precepts of the natural law as something to be done or avoided. (Aquinas 1270, Q94 Art.2)

So, third, linguistically competent people understand that “people’s good” analytically implies “worth doing and pursuing.” “People’s evil (bad)” implies to “to be avoided.” These connections point to the basis of substantive moral judgments.

Many experiences and states are preconceptually and intrinsically action-scaled, having positive or negative magnitude: pursue or avoid, a lot or a little. As pattern-seekers, human beings conceptualize and name these primitively felt experiences and states as pleasure and pain, serenity and fear, satisfaction and discontent, vitality and fatigue, self-esteem and shame, engagement and apathy, etc. More broadly, we conceptualize and name them and their causes as *good* and *bad*, which inherit their pursue-or-avoid, reason-to-act meaning from the experiences they categorize. That is, we call things good and bad because we have found them to be worth pursuing or avoiding. “[O]f the Reality of...Good and Ill [in the species], no rational Creature can possibly be insensible” (Shaftesbury 2001, v.2:24).

Because the world is full of good and bad things that cannot all be acted on at once (or in a lifetime), priorities are needed. In the nature of particular action-scaled experiences, and in the abstract terms by which we categorize and compare those experiences, whatever is overall more worthy of pursuit or avoidance is more reason to act, therefore more justified and therefore (from §1) morally better than less worthy alternatives, other things being equal. Comparative value, the greater good criterion, GGC, is therefore foundational to moral justification. Like unknowns in algebraic equations that can be determined from knowns, the GGC can be solved for substantive overall and moral better and worse by (usually qualitatively) comparing the pursue (good) and avoid (bad) experiences and states that are at stake in a situation. In this way, natural value facts give rise to prescriptive normative facts, the “is” to “ought” relationship that troubled Hume. Because it *is better* not to torture babies, there is more reason, so one *ought*, not to torture babies. (See also Peter Railton in Parfit 2017, 105-106.)

It is analytically obvious to linguistically competent people that greater value is greater reason to act, which might be why Mill did not argue the point, why ‘good’ has been near the center of Western moral philosophy at least since Plato called Good the highest Form, why Aquinas centered it, and why the GGC is intuitively compelling. Good, bad, better and worse are concepts by which we model, reason and communicate about action-scaled experiences and their role in choice and rational justification. Analytically and synthetically, abstractly and particularly, greater pursue or avoid value is greater reason to act, to pursue or avoid.

None of this, however, addresses “other things being equal” or shows that comparative value is *uniquely* foundational. Perhaps other things are justifying and can override a greater good. To do so, however, they must include some component that 1) has no value but matters enough, when combined with the action’s lesser value, to be overriding and 2) does not disrespect the losers in the suboptimal trade-off. Unless such components can be identified and shown to make more rational sense than a greater good, putative exceptions to the GGC are best explained as errors of judgment, leaving comparative value as the sole criterion by which to morally justify actions (§4-§7).

Corollary: Comparative value makes *actions* morally better or worse. Character and motives make *agents* morally better or worse. Because moral better and worse can refer to either actions or agents, and they do not always coincide – right actions can be ignobly motivated, such as for praise – they should not be conflated. Herein, moral better and worse refer to actions.

3. A Sketch of Morally Salient Value

The GGC fills the abstract placeholder-variable ‘more rational justification’ – which makes actions morally better (§1) – with ‘more value’, where the abstract ‘value’ is itself a placeholder for that which has been experienced to be worth pursuing (good) or avoiding (bad). The following sketch of value, inherent worth and respect expands the account in §2.

From the beginnings of life on Earth organisms have evolved capabilities by which to at least survive and propagate. We can agree with Aristotle that human capabilities include metabolism, sentience (sensings, including pleasure and pain) and reason. Good health, pleasure and sound reasoning are correspondingly experienced as positively action-scaled and worth pursuing. We conceptualize these states as *intrinsically good for us*, and that which promotes them as

instrumentally good for us. Ill health, suffering, faulty reasoning and their causes are negatively action-scalared, worth avoiding and *bad for* us. Some other value-bearing human capabilities are sociality, creativity and aesthetic and self-fulfillment sensibilities (and see Nussbaum 2000).

As individuals who matter to ourselves and care about our own well-being, we regard ourselves as ends having inherent worth (hereafter, just ‘worth’) and want others to respect us and consider what is good and bad for us. As pattern-seeking beings, beginning even as children – barring indoctrination to the contrary – we recognize from other people’s and organisms’ appearance and behavior that they are like us in having all or some of these capabilities, good-fors, bad-fors and worth meriting respect and consideration.

So, capabilities confer worth. Descartes and Kant attributed worth only to beings having the capacity to reason, Bentham and Mill only to beings that can feel pleasure and pain. A pragmatic alternative builds on Aristotle’s pluralism and attributes worth in proportion to an entity’s capabilities, such as rational sentient living beings more than merely sentient living beings more than merely living things more than rocks. Even if worth is instead conceived as binary rather than gradational, the required respect and consideration are proportionate to a being’s worth-conferring capabilities.

Another pragmatic practice is to attribute equal worth meriting equal respect to entities having the same *kinds* of capabilities, such as members of a species, even if individuals’ capabilities are not shared in equal measure. This is the basis of human rights, such as procedural equality under the law. A second kind of respect derives from people’s (and animals’) character and behavior. It is variable and can justify different treatment, such as different penalties under the law for the same crime and, in overcrowded lifeboats, different trade-offs among people having equal inherent worth but unequal instrumental value in the world.

The specific grounds, degrees and thresholds of worth are imprecise and contentious – Plants? Gnats? Fish? Cows? Ecosystems? Gaia? Artificial superintelligences? – but the idea is generally serviceable. Underdetermination and complexity should not obscure the obvious: Pleasure is intrinsically better than pain, functioning capabilities are better than malfunctioning ones, and richer sets of capability-based good-fors and bad-fors are why human beings have greater worth and deserve more respect and consideration than gnats. With Aristotle again, we should expect no more precision, certainty or consensus in practical morality than the subject matter affords.

In sum, capabilities and pursue (good) and avoid (bad) experiences are the ground of worth, respect and evaluative comparisons. The valence (good or bad), magnitude and probability of an action's effects on worth-weighted entities are the information needed to assess, compare and choose the greater good, thereby to respect and consider those entities in due, fair proportion and to justify those actions. We now consider nonconsequentialist views.

4. Kantian Deontology

Immanuel Kant rejects consequences as criteria of rightness and instead proposes a categorical, or unconditional, imperative (CI) by which to test rules for acting (1785). Kant formulates the CI in several ways.

The first prohibits acting on any rule that cannot be willed to be a universal law (FUL). Kant argues that the rule 'I may lie to avoid paying a debt I do not want to pay' is conceptually and practically contradictory, so it cannot be universally willed and is prohibited by FUL. He ultimately concludes that FUL prohibits all lies, but even Kantians tend to agree that the rule 'I may lie to prevent a murder' is universalizable. FUL applies to *relevantly similar* cases, and lying to avoid paying a debt differs relevantly from lying to prevent a murder, differentiated most obviously by the values at stake.

Kant's second formulation, of humanity or the end-in-itself (FEI), requires treating or using rationally autonomous beings – humanity, including oneself – always as ends in themselves, never as mere means. All such beings have incomparable worth, Kant says, so respecting them prohibits interfering with their rational autonomy, the sole basis of worth according to Kant. Lying does interfere and treats people as mere means, so FEI absolutely prohibits it. But interference, whether by action or inaction, is sometimes unavoidable: A person can be fully respected yet rightly lied to – treated, used – as a mere means to prevent a murder because being lied to interferes with rational autonomy less than does being dead. Beings have an absolute right to be respected and considered as ends in themselves in proportion to their worth, but not an absolute right never to be treated or used as a mere means. So we change 'treat' to 'respect.' As a formal principle FEI should also accommodate conceptions of worth beyond rational agency. So, as modified, mFEI: *Always respect beings as ends in themselves in proportion to their (finite) inherent worth.* Proportionate respect is a condition of impartial value comparisons and of relevant similarity in FUL.

Moral rules apply universally to relevantly similar situations (FUL). Beings merit respect in proportion to their worth (mFEI). Respect requires considering how beings of worth are affected, where greater overall value or disvalue is more justifying reason to pursue or avoid an outcome (GGC). FUL, mFEI and the GGC are conceptually foundational, absolute, imposed by reason and autonomously self-legislatable. The GGC presumes the logic of universalizability (FUL), requires proportionate respect (mFEI), and implies Kant's other formulations of the categorical imperative, the Law of Nature and the Kingdom of Ends. (Cummiskey 1996, Hare 1997 and Kagan 2002 argue in overlapping ways that Kant and consequentialism converge.)

5. Social Contracts

Contract theorists John Rawls and T. M. Scanlon reject consequentialism and instead devise principles of social justice (Rawls 1971) and personal interaction (Scanlon 1998). They argue that reasonable, normally self-interested people would find these principles generally acceptable or nonrejectable within the respective specified domains.

Rawls believed people would reject consequentialist systems of justice because, from behind an imagined 'veil of ignorance,' knowing no differentiating facts about themselves or their socioeconomic position, they would fear that their own primary social goods – liberty, opportunity and wealth – could be taken at any time in any measure to serve a greater good. Such a system would be unstable, Rawls argues. He instead proposes a system of mutually compatible, lexically ordered liberties, opportunities and wealth, such that the liberties cannot be traded away for greater opportunities, which in turn cannot be traded for greater total societal wealth. The 'difference principle' allocates resources to ensure that less advantaged individuals have sufficient means to benefit from the guaranteed liberties and opportunities, while keeping taxes low enough not to disincentivize productivity. Rawls argues that in prosperous economies this system would freely, fairly, acceptably and stably enable all, as far as they are individually able, to take advantage of equal opportunities and pursue reasonable conceptions of the good.

Ironically and not coincidentally, Rawls' emphases on stability, liberty, opportunity and means to pursue reasonable personal conceptions of the good mirror Mill's utilitarian account. Mill says people have "the strongest interest" in liberty to pursue their own good (1985, 256), which requires opportunity and, much like the difference principle, creates "an equal claim to all the means of happiness...except insofar as the inevitable conditions of human life...set limits"

(258). Likewise, security, or stability, is needed “for the whole value of all and every good, beyond the passing moment” (251). Mill argues that these components of justice are necessary for the greater good and justified by it. In large measure, Rawls recapitulates Mill and undermines his own conception and critique of consequentialist justice.

Scanlon’s motivating premise is that actions must be justifiable to all who are affected. He argues that a moral principle can be reasonably rejected by anyone on whom it imposes an unreasonable burden. He says consequentialism should be rejected because no number of small benefits for some can make another’s great suffering reasonable. The proper comparison is therefore not one-to-a-sum, Scanlon says, but *one-to-one*, one person’s suffering to another’s small benefit, where a strong individual claim lexically trumps any number of lesser opposing claims. A claim’s weight resides in generally recognizable burdens, not merely in the affected person’s subjective sensibility, so one-to-one claims can be made on behalf of those who cannot do so for themselves, such as babies, the mentally disabled, future generations and animals.

Scanlon frames duty-based claims in terms of burdens, which in turn reflect, or are, generally recognized ‘bad-fors.’ Moral claims are therefore reducible to implicated values, so the remaining question is whether comparisons must be one-to-one.

One-to-one comparisons are indeterminate when the choice is one versus a number of equal claims. In these cases Scanlon says the number is decisive. Further, when the trade-off is one versus multiple lesser claims, Scanlon says that both the number and magnitude of the claims matter until, on a continuum of decreasing magnitude, the threshold of lexicality is reached and the numbers become irrelevant. Scanlon makes similar allowances in many-versus-many policy decisions. None of these is value aggregation by another name, he says, because they are grounded in individual burden-based rejectability, but burdens are bad-fors, and Scanlon says they are to be weighed and counted in these cases, so the purpose, assessment and results differ little from value aggregation, the GGC.

Further, although Scanlon’s ‘reasonable rejectability’ is meant to accommodate normal human self-interest, it does not make less-than-best actions morally better. Understood instead as justification rather than permission, ‘reasonable’ becomes ‘rational’ (§1), the informed impartial weighing of all affected persons’ valid claims, conditions and capacities.

Lastly, consequentialists can agree with and accommodate Scanlon's complaint that one person's severe suffering is not justifiable by any number of others' small benefits. Like Scanlon, they can do this by incorporating lexical thresholds into value theory. In short, Scanlon's view of what we owe to others merges with the GGC.

Derek Parfit's 'triple theory' seeks to reconcile consequentialism with social contract theories. He says these theories are climbing different sides of the same mountain, where moral principles at the summit would satisfy essential elements of each and be compatible with widely held moral intuitions. But he also argues that such principles will be universally rationally willable or non-rejectable only if they are optimific (2011, Vol.1, 413). Parfit fills the optimific placeholder with rule consequentialism because he believes some moral intuitions fatally contradict act consequentialism (417), but he also acknowledges that making things go best means that situationally optimific exceptions override useful, generally optimific rules, which points back to act consequentialism as the more fundamental principle.

The theories of Kant, Rawls, Scanlon and Parfit arguably merge into or are subsidiary to act consequentialism, the GGC, which applies to all (not domain-limited) situations involving choices by moral agents that affect beings of worth. The GGC justifies (acts of) creating and honoring contracts, rights, procedures, policies, institutions and interpersonal norms – Mill's "secondary principles" – that produce more value than the alternatives. It justifies (acts of) revising, rejecting or situationally violating such constructs when doing so would make things go better – taking risk into account – as determined by probabilities of realizing all-the-way-down good-fors and bad-fors for proportionately respected beings of worth, which are what fundamentally matter and challenge intuitions to the contrary.

6. Moral Intuitions and Virtues

Moral intuitions and virtues tend to be value-positive and justifiable by the GGC. Some, however, conflict with the GGC and are used as counterexamples against it. Consequentialists parry with the intuition that acting for the greatest good is always permissible. But I argue in this section that moral intuitions and ordinary virtues are useful but fallible moral indicators, neither self-justifying nor validly justified apart from the not-*merely*-intuited GGC (§2, §3).

Intuitionists and virtue ethicists argue that right and wrong are knowable but not systematically justifiable or reducible to a single principle. W.D. Ross (1930) says we intuitively "see" honesty,

non-harm, fairness, beneficence, gratitude, etc. as irreducible duties, which sometimes override a greater good. Words that name duties also tend to name virtues, and virtue ethicists say, in short, that right and wrong are determined by what virtuous people do. Duties and virtues are not absolute, however, so conflicts between intuitively-based honesty and loyalty, say, must also be decided intuitively. Values are relevant but not inherently decisive.

Although intuitions can seem to be “just knowing” portals to truth, they are better understood as attitude-based reactions, where attitudes are settled propensities to automatically react favorably or unfavorably to a stimulus when it, the attitude object, comes to one’s attention (Rokeach 1968). Attitudes form when causal sequences of stimulus, response and pursue-or-avoid outcomes become neurally embedded. Pleasure, pain and startle and fall instincts evolved as pursue-or-avoid reactions, the genetically encoded embodiment of attitudes to actual and potential benefit and harm. These reactions produce a host of secondary attitudes toward their particular causes. Attitudes can also be assimilated from culture (racism, hospitality) or individually unique experiences (distrust, tastes in food) (Greene 2014, 714). Once an attitude is in place, the mere thought of the attitude object can produce a reaction from the embedded pursue-or-avoid association.

Some attitudes pertain to kinds of actions and produce intuitions of duty, right and wrong. “Seeing” duties – honesty, beneficence, fairness, etc. – can be explained as reactions to perceived or anticipated benefits and harms. I will refer to direct right or wrong intuitions as **DRWIns**, a reminder of their adaptive, positive-value origins, whether or not they were initially recognized or are consciously remembered as such. DRWIns are undeliberated, quick, affectively motivating and, from their beneficial pursue-or-avoid origins, ordinarily good and justifiable by the GGC.

Attitudes can nonetheless be situationally unfitting. Percussive sounds and people darting from doorways should prompt different reactions in urban warfare and holiday shopping. Reactions adapted to abusive relationships can thwart caring relationships. An intuition that inhibits lying is misplaced when a lie would prevent a murder. A DRWIn’s reliability depends on the stimulus *and the context* being relevantly similar to that of the underlying attitude’s value-adding origins (Green 2014, 714-715).

So: DRWIns and virtue-habits are situationally fallible, neither self-justifying nor justified by having been intuited, nor by a sense of certainty, nor by the intuiter’s usual reliability or position

of power or authority (Plato's Euthyphro dilemma). "A test of right and wrong must be the means, one would think, of ascertaining what is right or wrong, and not a consequence of having already [intuitively] ascertained it" (Mill 1985, 206). Intuitive and virtuous people are recognized as reliable because they have a history of good judgment as otherwise determined. Moral intuitions are in this way like a mathematician's intuited theorem or an architect's novel structural design, which require validation by independent criteria or tests.

As a moral criterion the GGC justifies greater-good DRWIns, while DRWIns contrary to a greater good are more likely out of their original value-adding context and therefore of doubtful reliability. If they nonetheless feel certain and are presumed to be valid, they need some other justification, which requires components that 1) matter but have no value and 2) do not disrespect the losers in the suboptimal trade-off.

One explanation is that commitments, such as promises, satisfy the two requirements and override a greater good 1) by creating obligations that matter beyond their purposive value and 2) by legitimately prioritizing parties to a commitment over others affected. Commitments do matter beyond their intended purpose in the value of relationships and trust that can be lost when a commitment is broken, but a component that matters without value remains unidentified.

Likewise, parties to a commitment are legitimately prioritized because values particular to the commitment apply directly to them, but it is the values, not the person, which add moral weight.

Another explanation is that rights can override a greater good. Rights matter for their value, but again, how they also matter without value is unidentified. Likewise, an explanation of how the losers in suboptimal trade-offs are not being disrespected is absent. The morally foundational human right to equal respect arguably underlies all other rights and cannot be superseded.

There is also the Rossian explanation that intuitions of right and wrong are as valid as and can supersede intuitions of value. But if something like the account in §2 and §3 is accepted, the intrinsic values that ultimately inform the GGC are not intuited. They are direct, stand-alone pursue (good) or avoid (bad) experiences – pleasure, pain, calm, fear, vitality, fatigue, satisfaction, discontent, self-esteem, shame, etc. They tell us what is worth pursuing and avoiding, but not what to act on until compared to the alternatives. DRWIns, on the other hand, derive from and are reducible to these values, and they are fallible, comparative and directive: Do this, not the alternatives. The 'intuitions are intuitions' argument misses the target.

DRWIns and virtue-habits are cognitively efficient but fallible heuristic proxies for ‘more rationally justified’ and ‘morally better.’ At the same time, while deliberated value comparisons and held instrumental values are oriented toward greater value, they, too, are fallible. Intuitions and deliberations, alike, can be misdirected by complexity, false or incomplete information and biases such as short-sightedness, self-interest, racism, sexism and religionism. Even given the same information, these differently evolved epistemic processes can be differently prescriptive. Experience and reflection are the corrective. “A taste or judgment...can hardly come ready formed with us into the world...Use, practice and culture must precede the understanding” (Shaftesbury 2001 [1732], v3:101). “The primitive spontaneous processes of the mind are mixed with error, which is only to be removed gradually by comprehensive reflection upon the results of these processes” (Sidgwick 1876, 564). Intuition and deliberation inform but do not supplant or compete with the greater good as the criterion of moral better and worse. By denying unifying principles and treating DRWIns and other moral habits as independently authoritative, intuitionists and virtue ethicists make “ethics not so much a guide as a consecration of men’s actual sentiments” (Mill 1985, 207).

7. Other Critiques

I have argued that Kant’s modified categorical imperative; Rawls’ and Scanlon’s contract theories; Parfit’s triple theory; and intuitionist, virtuous and deliberative epistemic processes are best understood as operating within a consequentialist domain defined by the GGC. This section addresses related objections.

Justification Gaps. Ordinarily, promise-keeping is intuitive, value-adding and justifiable by the greater good. Unordinarily, promise-*breaking* has greater value and is justified as such. Still, some actions seem morally better and overall worse: Keep a promise even if it prevents two other people from keeping theirs, and do not kill an innocent even to save more innocents. Such cases fall in justification gaps between ordinary and unordinary greater goods, gaps that need to be either explained away or justified with components that matter but have no value and do not disrespect the losers in the suboptimal trade-off.

Breaking promises. Imagine that Pat, Chris and Steph are walking together, each to different lunch meetings. On the way they encounter an injured person. No one else is nearby. Agreeing that they must help, they realize that either Pat alone or Chris and Steph together can provide the

needed aid. The promises to meet for lunch are of equal importance, so the justifiable choice is for Pat to help, willingly breaking the promise so the other two promises can be kept, because it is the greater good. Agents who know their own but not others' situations and motives might justly keep their own promises as the greater *ensured* good – a bird in the hand versus two in the bush. But if another person's promise is more important and requires breaking one's own, and the person is known to be trustworthy, one ought to break one's own. The GGC applies.

Harming innocents: Trolley. Most people say it would be morally wrong to push a large person off a footbridge onto the track below to stop an out-of-control trolley, killing that person in order to save five others farther down the track who cannot get out of the way. By contrast, in the 'Switch' scenario most respondents morally approve throwing a switch to divert the trolley onto another track, saving the five but killing one a mile away. (Stipulations: We are to accept, however improbably, that the agent immediately and certainly knows that the trolley is out of control; that pushing and switching, or not, are the only options; and what the outcomes of each would be.)

Respondents are perplexed when asked to reconcile their opposite answers, the greater good in Switch and the greater bad in Footbridge. In Switch, concern for the five prevails over the more distant, less direct killing of the one and is justified by the GGC. In Footbridge, the response can be causally explained and perhaps excused by the affective intensity against repugnant, traumatizing, hard-to-explain-to-others hands-on killing; the fear of culpability and punishment; and perhaps knowing that in reality one would not know as stipulated. These reactions understandably overwhelm attitudes, empathy and respect felt for the more distant five who, most say, should be allowed to die. But the question is what is morally justified, not what an agent would or could do.

The inverse correlation between intensity of affect and psycho-physical distance in the two scenarios suggests that common intuitions – that an innocent should not be directly harmed even to save more innocents, that doing harm is morally worse than allowing the same harm, and that doing harm up close is morally worse than doing the same harm at a distance – are better explained by out-of-original-context attitudes than by rational justifications. The greater number of innocent strangers' absolute right to equal respect contradicts and invalidates these intuitions, absent a rational explanation to the contrary.

Such trade-offs are not limited to thought experiments, and sacrificing an innocent or loved one to save a greater number of innocents can be at once monstrous and heroic. Pondering whether to save the life of a stranger rather than a loved one is indeed “one thought too many,” but when the strangers number five, five hundred or five hundred thousand, or when there is a choice between a night on the town and feeding the hungry, *not* pondering is irrational and irresponsible.

Common virtues are virtues because they are efficient, usually beneficial and reflect ordinarily fitting attitudes, but they are not virtuous when they permit a clearly greater harm. A person who can push in Footbridge might be the rare one needed to do a horrible thing to prevent a much worse thing.

These kinds of cases recall Plato’s metaphor of the parts of the soul (*Phaedrus*): A skittish horse can prevent a rational charioteer from reaching the destination. Nights on the town and emotionally charged DRWIns can be more motivating than cool assessments of a greater good. Reason can be a weakly interacting mental process, a WIMP.

Consequentializing. Consequentializers seek to eliminate justification gaps by showing how right-but-less-good intuitions can be the greater good after all. One tactic proposes other value types, such as that promise-keeping is good in itself and can make keeping an otherwise less good promise overall better. But promises are not beings of worth, so it is unclear why we should be concerned about them apart from their effects on beings of worth. Such other value types add ontological complexity and perplexity, and they cannot plausibly justify a DRWIn that elevates the life of one innocent stranger over the lives of five other innocent strangers who have a right to equal respect. Another tactic would justify the five deaths in terms of the evaluator’s held values rather than by values and worth considered impartially. Although agent-relative interests can contribute to the greater good (see Alienation, below), they can also be an idiosyncratic slippery slope of harmful rationalization.

Justification gaps are more plausibly, if not more comfortably, understood as errors of judgment than as situations that override the GGC and need justifications that add complexity and invite Occam’s razor.

Alienation and Agent-Centered Prerogatives. Critics of the GGC say the impartiality needed to assess and act for an overall greater good unacceptably alienates us from core human values such as personal projects and relationships that make life worth living and can be realized in no

other way. But consequentialists, too, accept these values, and add that the greater good would not be achieved by everyone wholly sacrificing these things in the service of others who are wholly sacrificing these things. Paraphrasing Charles Schulz's *Peanuts*, Lucy says, "Charlie Brown, what do you think we're here for?" Charlie Brown, "I think it's to help others." Lucy, "What are the others here for?" Balanced, limited partialities are impartially justifiable as contributors to a greater good.

Framed differently, critics say consequentialism is alienating because it makes aggregates, rather than persons, the objects of moral concern. But when the affected parties are too many to be considered individually, the GGC is no more alienating than other theories, nor does it preclude empathy for anonymous strangers whose well-being is what matters and constitutes the aggregate ("Oh, the humanity!"). Too little partiality alienates us from those who matter most to us and for whom we can do the most good, including ourselves. Too much partiality alienates us from everything else. Pay special attention to those you love, but do not cheat on their behalf. Limited partialities are impartially justifiable contributors to the greater good.

Justice and Fairness. Thought experiments distribute hypothetical units of value – 'utils' or 'hedons' – in various ways to show that fairness sometimes matters more than a greater good. But the aspects of well-being represented by utils and hedons, such as health and happiness, cannot simply be traded from one person to another and must not be conflated with the resources they require, which can be redistributed.

Distributive justice allocates resources toward greatest marginal utility, which is greatest value. The impossibility of knowing all aspects of everyone's well-being and of individually fine-tuning allocations points to the need for systems like Mill's and Rawls' that secure basic needs, do not disincentivize productivity, and provide the personal and societal benefits of equal respect, opportunity and liberty to pursue reasonable conceptions of the good within the inevitable economic and personal limitations of human life, thereby justly maximizing the potential for autonomous agents' well-being across a population, the greater good.

Different kinds of justice can conflict:

[T]o save a life, it may not only be allowable, but a duty, to steal, or take by force, the necessary food or medicine, or to kidnap, and compel to officiate, the only qualified medical practitioner. In such cases...we usually say, not that justice must give way to some other

moral principle, but that what is just in ordinary cases is, by reason of that other principle, not just in the particular case. By this useful accommodation of language, the character of indefeasibility attributed to justice is kept up. (Mill 1985, 259)

Being lied to, robbed, kidnapped or run over by a trolley so that more may live are bad, undeserved and unfair to the innocent victims of circumstance, but the alternatives are bad, undeserved and unfair to a greater number of innocents of equal worth. Even just trade-offs create winners and losers and are unfortunately sometimes the lesser evil.

Robert Nozick's 'utility monster' is an imaginary glutton that derives more and undiminishing pleasure from eating than people can. On that premise the GGC would presumably and counterintuitively allocate all food to the monster. But the first person to feel hunger pain arguably reverses the case. Or perhaps children's despair at never having a cookie outweighs the monster's pleasure. Or if gustatory pleasure is the monster's only good-for, greater human worth based on multiple good-fors that require food reverses the case. But if the monster needs all the food to support good-fors and worth that exceed ours by as much as ours exceed a gnat's, then, sadly for us, proportionate respect would justify treating us like gnats by comparison. Either way, the GGC gets it distributively right, fairly and justly, with winners and losers.

The valence, magnitude and probability of realizing the values at stake are the information needed to apply the GGC by respecting and considering affected parties in due, fair and just proportion to which every entity of worth has an absolute right. The GGC and justice require proportionate respect for beings of worth whose well-being is what matters.

The Repugnant Conclusion. Imagine worlds A and Z. World A is populated by a few billion people who all have very good lives, while lives on world Z are all barely worth living but in such great numbers that the total value exceeds that of world A, counterintuitively making Z the better world. This is Parfit's Repugnant Conclusion (1984, 381ff), which challenges the GGC and any theory in which human well-being matters. Parfit saw no resolution.

To clarify, lives barely worth living are by definition barely better than death, but lives can be both bad – better never to have been born – and worth living if the alternative – dying – is perceived to be worse. For Z to be better than A, its many lives must be barely more good than bad and not as repugnant as “barely worth living” might seem. But they are still impoverished and deprived, so despite the great number of barely good lives Z still seems worse than A.

Attempts to eliminate the paradox offer various ways to show that world A is better than Z, but each raises other problems and none has succeeded. A possibly novel adaptation is based on worth-conferring capabilities (§3): World A lexically trumps Z because it provides opportunities for everyone to explore and realize their natural capabilities, whereas on Z some capabilities that make us fully human are realizable by no one, and people's lives as lived are less than fully human. Z is indeed worse than A.

A gradual narrowing between extremes in Parfit's (and Scanlon's) cases raises the question of when the threshold of lexicality has been crossed. The many variables can make comparisons of worlds and societies imprecise and uncertain, but they do not undermine the principle that overall better is rationally more to be pursued and morally better. Questions in value theory pertain to how to apply the GGC, not to its validity.

An epistemic objection is that the long-term effects and value of actions are unknowable, so the greater good criterion is useless. But the countless shorter-term betters that can reliably be brought about can be expected to outweigh the occasional unpredictable worses, and intentional predictable worses would not often be outweighed by unpredictable betters. These probabilities justify pursuing predictable greater goods and avoiding predictable greater bads.

Demandingness. The logical terminus of the GGC is maximizing: There is most reason and most justification to do what is overall best. Less-than-best actions are less justified and less moral. The objection is that, by constantly requiring best, consequentialism is too demanding. But although consequentialists concur that overall better and worse are the criteria of moral better and worse, the semantics and thresholds of demandingness and rightness vary and resist definition (Sosa 1993, 115-118; Norcross 2020). Samples: Only the best action is right and required, or best is right but not necessarily required, or rightness is proportional across a range of actions. Or morality is like a puzzle with criteria for getting it right but which makes no demands, so demands are self-imposed, or not. Morally conscientious people aspire to get it right. Less conscientious people deserve to be respected in their autonomy, within limits. In both cases, it is overall and morally better to permit limited prerogatives than to always demand a clear or imagined best, especially as applied to others. But most conclusively, the purpose of moral inquiry is clarity of understanding, wherever it leads, not relief from moral burdens (Butchvarov 1989, 23).

I have argued that comparative value is foundational to moral justification (§1-§3) and that other normative theories and objections do not undermine the GGC or provide sound alternatives to it (§4-§7), leaving it as the exclusive criterion of justification.

8. The Greater Good Criterion

Mill's Greatest Happiness Principle is a starting point toward a formal statement of the GGC:

Actions are right in proportion as they tend to promote happiness, wrong as they tend to produce the reverse of happiness. (1985, 210)

First, from §3, replace 'happiness' with 'value for entities of inherent worth.'

Next, the moral status of actions is determined not just by the value they produce, but by the value they produce compared to an agent's possible alternatives. If the widow's donated mite is the best her poverty allows it is morally best and morally better than the rich man's larger donation that does more good but is not the best he could do. (Their moral characters, on the other hand, are in their motives. Perhaps the widow gives publicly and only for sympathy and praise, while the rich man gives anonymously and only to help.)

Clarify 'tend' by replacing it with 'are reasonably expected' (Jackson 1991). Lying is usually worse than not lying, but a lie that prevents a murder is an exception. Rational justification depends on the reasonably expected value of reasonably expected outcomes. Although outcomes reveal an action's actual value after the fact, they do not in hindsight make the action *morally* better or worse, right or wrong. If they did, rational agents sometimes ought to do that which they have no knowable reason to do. Example: If a car speeding around a curve on the wrong side of the road cannot be seen by an oncoming driver, it would by luck be good but not right or rationally justified for the oncoming driver to also be on the wrong side.

Reasonable expectations require due diligence, the situationally appropriate effort to understand and weigh the values and probabilities at stake. Due diligence in activities of daily life is less demanding than due diligence in choosing long-term projects such as relationships, education, career and service that come to populate the activities of daily life. In all cases, long- or short-term, duly diligent choices need to be reconsidered only as new information warrants. As in §5, equitable laws, policies, rights, contracts and other norms make continual questioning counterproductive.

The greater good criterion (GGC):

An action is morally better (or worse) in proportion to the overall value (or disvalue) for proportionately respected and weighed entities of inherent worth a duly diligent rational agent expects to produce by performing it, compared to the agent's other possible actions.

Possible actions are limited by context and the agent's psychological and physical ability, subject to due diligence.

The ideal imperative – “Do the most good you can do” (Singer 2015) – applies well to highly consequential decisions and projects, even if the most good that can be done is uncertain.

Otherwise, “Do more good” and “Be kind” are easier everyday reminders that deemphasize the more onerous ‘most.’

9. Summary and Conclusion

The moral domain requires rational agents and rational justifications. Greater rational justification makes an action morally better than less justified alternatives. Primitively experienced pursue (good) and avoid (bad) states are intrinsic justifying reasons to act, where a greater good or bad is greater reason to act, to pursue or avoid. Organisms' capacity-based good-fors and bad-fors confer inherent worth, which merits respect and consideration in proportion to types of capacities. Therefore, a worth-weighted, duly diligently expected overall greater good is more proportionately respectful, more fair, more rational reason to act and therefore more justified and morally better than less good alternatives. Values and the greater good can be situationally simple and obvious or complex, uncertain, underdetermined and contentious.

Critics of the GGC insist that some actions are morally better than overall better alternatives, but they have not successfully described components necessary to justify less-good actions, that 1) have no value but matter enough, when combined with the action's lesser value, to override a greater good, and 2) do not disrespect the losers in suboptimal trade-offs. Nonconsequentialist attempts at justification fare poorly against the clear logic of the GGC and experientially established values, although the motivating force of greater good reasoning does not always prevail over strongly held convictions and affects to the contrary.

Norms and controls on human behavior have evolved over millennia. Diverse cultural traditions, semantic conventions, intellectual histories and held values, beliefs and attitudes are more or

less, but not equally, value-adding. These differences help explain why “after more than two thousand years the same discussions continue” regarding the foundations of morality. But if moral theories are climbing different sides of the same mountain, the greater good criterion controls the summit. Other normative theories converge with or are explicable and criterially superseded by it. Practical moral disputes then concern not foundational principles, but values, worth and probabilities by which to determine the greater good.

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